

Renewable Energy and Make in India Opportunities: A Brief Study

Dr. Lokanath Paital

Ph.D. & Author

E-mail ID : lokanathpaital@gmail.com

Abstract

'Energy' means life and the 21st century is completely based on it due to drastic and sustainable need of the developments in every sphere of human beings. Energy means development and development leads to prosperous and prosperous leads to the least conflicts or violent due to huge economic disparity among the countries in the world. So the need of the hour demand for energy and associated services to meet social and economic development and improve human welfare and health is increasing. According to IMF World Economic Outlook-2021, India has become the third largest economy of the world after China and America on the basis of purchasing power parity with 10.207 trillion dollar and 6th in the world on the basis of nominal GDP. It is expected that, India to be the most populated country as well as the largest economy in the world by 2050. That's why the demand for energy is going to increase substantially even if we manage to maintain the present trend in per capita energy need for without compromising its growth. Energy can play the most important role in the modern world. In this connection, 'The Make in India' Program is going to further enhance the energy need of the country though it aims to attain 'Zero Defect and Zero Effect'. To attain Zero Effect we need to control CO₂ emission by increasing dependence on *Clean and Green Technology*. This article mainly highlights how the renewable energy to fulfill the growing needs of the world's second largest population through 'Make in India Programmes' and create many opportunities in the country.

Keywords : Sustainable Development, IMF World Economic Outlook, Trillion Dollar, Zero Defect, Zero Effect, Emission, Clean and Green Technology, Make in India.

Introduction:

'Energy' means life and the 21st century is completely based on it due to drastic and sustainable need of the developments in every sphere of human beings. So the need of the hour demand for energy associated services, to meet social and economic development and improve welfare and health, is increasing.¹ All societies require energy services to meet basic human needs like lighting, cooking, space comfort, mobility and communication and to serve productive processes. Since approximately 1850, global use of fossil fuels (coal, oil and gas) has increased to dominate energy supply to a rapid growth in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions.²

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions resulting from the provision of energy services have contributed significantly to the historic increase in atmospheric GHG concentrations. The IPCC Fourth Assessment Report concluded that "Most of the observed increase in global average temperature since the mid 20th century is very likely due to the observed increase in anthropogenic greenhouse gas concentrations. Recent data confirm that consumption of fossil fuels accounts for the major global anthropogenic GHG emissions. Emissions continue to grow and CO₂ concentrations had increased to over 390 PPM, or 39% above preindustrial levels, by the end of 2010. There are many options for lowering GHG emissions from the energy system while still satisfying the global demand for energy services.³ Regarding this issue, Renewable Energy (RE) is the best option to solve this problem and to support the rising demand of people in the 21st century.⁴ Renewable Energy (RE) comprises a heterogeneous class of technologies that

are able to satisfy multiple energy service needs of human beings. Some RE technologies can be deployed at the point of use (decentralized) in rural and urban environments whereas others are primarily deployed within large (centralized) energy networks. Though a growing number of RE technologies are technically mature and are being deployed at significant scale, others are in an earlier phase of technical maturity and commercial deployment.⁵ On the other hand, the global economy's need for energy continues to rise, requiring more energy than is ultimately available from nonrenewable resources. Rising demand (60 percent from 2005 to 2015) is likely to change the current distribution of sources on which the world relies to meet its energy needs (left). As the fossil free energy scenario prediction (right) suggests, it would be possible to tap renewable sources to meet the world's entire energy needs by the end of the twenty-first century. For example, it is estimated that more than 50 Global South countries could produce as much energy from the biomass residues generated by sugar production as they presently obtain from oil; that less than 5 percent of the globe's small-scale hydropower has been exploited; and that land-based wind turbines could provide 20 million megawatt-hours of electricity each year – twice as much as the world consumed in 1987.⁶ No doubt, RE from replaceable sources also has the advantage of doing relatively little damage to the environment. For these reasons, the presently little-used non-hydrocarbon sources of energy are expected to expand from 2005 to 2030 far more rapidly than the rates of hydrocarbons (oil, gas, and coal); solar by about 100 percent, wind by 250

percent, nuclear by 40 percent, and biomass by about 250 percent. Enthusiasm has been particularly strong for building “a hydrogen fuel economy” based on hydrogen use in fuel cells as a substitute for the “carbon economy”, because hydrogen provides opportunities to reduce dependence on foreign oil imports and rely on pollution-free hydrogen power to eliminate emissions that cause air quality problems. Nevertheless, despite the potential, fossil fuels’ share of world energy will likely remain very dominant, with RE sources probably accounting for only about 8 percent of the global energy supply by 2020.⁷ RE is useful energy that is collected from renewable resources, which are naturally replenished on a human timescale, including carbon neutral sources like sunlight, wind, rain, tides, waves and geothermal heat. This type of energy source stands in contrast to fossil fuels, which are being used far more quickly than they are being replenished. Although most RE is sustainable energy, some is not, for example some biomass is unsustainable.⁸ Based on REN21s 2017 report, renewables contributed 19.3% to humans’ global energy consumption and 24.5% to their generation of electricity in 2015 and 2016, respectively. This energy consumption is divided as 8.9% coming from traditional biomass, 4.2% as heat energy (modern biomass, geothermal and solar heat), 3.9% from hydroelectricity and the remaining 2.2% is electricity from wind, solar, geothermal and other forms of biomass. In 2017, worldwide investments in RE amounted to US\$279.8 billion with China accounting for 45% of the global investments, and the United States and Europe both around 15%. Globally there were an estimated 10.5 million jobs associated with the RE industries, with solar photovoltaics being the largest renewable employer. RE systems are rapidly becoming more efficient and cheaper and their share of total energy consumption is increasing. As of 2019, more than two-thirds of worldwide newly installed electricity capacity was renewable. Growth in consumption of coal and oil could end by 2020 due to increased uptake of renewables and natural gas. As of 2020, in most countries, photovoltaic solar and onshore wind are the cheapest forms of building new electricity-generating plants.

But according to Data, at the national level, at least 30 nations around the world already have RE contributing more than 20 percent of their energy supply. National renewable energy markets are projected to continue to grow strongly in the coming decade and beyond. At least two countries, Iceland and Norway, generate all their electricity using RE already, and many other countries have the set of goal to reach 100% renewable energy in the future. At least 47 nations around the world already have over 50 percent of electricity from renewable

resources. RE resources exist over wide geographical areas, in contrast to fossil fuels, which are concentrated in a limited number of countries. Rapid deployment of RE and energy efficiency technologies is resulting in significant energy security, climate change mitigation, and economic benefits. In international public opinion surveys there is strong support for promoting renewable sources such as solar power and wind power. Similarly, in the recent years many RE projects are large-scale, renewable technologies are also suited to rural and remote areas and developing countries, where energy is often crucial in human development. As most of RE technologies provide electricity, RE deployment is often applied in conjunction with further electrification, which has several benefits; electricity can be converted to heat, can be converted into mechanical energy with high efficiency, and is clean at the point of consumption. In addition, electrification with RE is more efficient and therefore leads to significant reductions in primary energy requirements.⁹ As we know, energy is one of the cornerstones of any burgeoning industrial power but, for developing countries like India, it is a matter of critical choices. Although India is one of the lowest per capita greenhouse gas contributor globally, its improving living standards, rising aspirational young population and the modernization of its industrial sectors portend that the country’s energy needs will grow at around three times the current global rate. Hence, the International Energy Authority has attributed one-quarter of the global growth in energy demand estimated upto 2040 to India. On the other hand, during recent years, India has been at the forefront of adopting innovative solutions in RE generation to support the rising demand. Projects involving biomass, hydropower, geothermal, wind and solar energy generation are being developed. India’s strategic plan is to integrate these technologies into the existing grid allowing for a flexible and secure energy supply that progressively substitutes for the fuel-stock use of coal, oil and solid biomass like wood, which totals almost 80% currently, to a 60% from RE source by 2030. The advent and policy thrust to renewable energy systems will require a paradigm shift in the management of energy transition and absorption. Specialized manpower for the purpose will be required to navigate this transition. Energy engineers will be required to manage what will be a new era in sustainable energy production and delivery. RE presents a huge window of opportunities for employment growth within the sector¹⁰ particularly in the biggest democratic country like India in the 21st century. According to IMF World Economic Outlook-2021, India has become the third largest economy of the world after China and America on the basis of the

purchasing power parity with 10.207 trillion dollar and sixth in the world on the basis of nominal GDP. It is expected that, India to be the most populated country as well as the largest economy in the world by 2050. But the most important fact is that, how the RE to fulfill the growing demands of the world's second largest population through 'Make in India Programmes' and create many opportunities in the country.

Objectives of the Study:

The present paper tries to address the following objectives.

- (i) To know the current position and future prospects of the Renewable Energy in India.
- (ii) To know India's targets 70% of our energy coming from renewable sources by 2050.
- (iii) To know how make in India opportunities impact in Renewable Energy Sector.
- (iv) To depict some constructive suggestions for the betterment of India and world.

Research Methodology:

The research work aims at the careful study of the subject undertaken in order to discover new fact or information about it. As no single method can be solely relied upon for acquiring a meaningful insight of this research article, therefore, a combination of Historical and Analytical method is applied in the study. For the historical and analytical method of study, the data has been collected from secondary sources as per the guidance. The secondary sources are –

- (i) Journals
- (ii) Articles
- (iii) Newspapers
- (iv) Official Documents
- (v) Reports
- (vi) Books
- (vii) Platform Speeches

Sources Of Renewable Energy :

Everything available in our environment which can be used to satisfy our needs provided. It is technologically accessible economically feasible and culturally acceptable can be termed as 'Resource'. The process of transformation of things available in our environment involves an interactive relationship between nature, technology and institutions. Human beings interact with nature through technology and create institutions to accelerate their economic development. Resources are a function of human activities. As human beings themselves are essential components of resources. These resources can be classified into the different ways but on the basis of exhaustibility, there are two kinds like, Renewable and Non-renewable. The most energy sources for doing work are non-renewable energy sources. These are, Petroleum, Hydrocarbon Gas Liquids, Natural Gas, Coal and Nuclear Energy. These energy sources are called non-renewable

because their supplies are limited to the amounts that we can mine or extract from the earth. Coal, Natural gas, and petroleum formed over thousands of years from the buried remains of ancient sea plants and animals that lived millions of years ago. That is why we also call those energy sources fossil fuels.¹¹ Similarly, the major sources or types of RE in the modern days are Solar Energy from the sun, Geothermal Energy from heat inside the earth, Wind Energy, Biomass from plants and Hydropower from flowing water. They are called RE sources because they are naturally replenished. Day after day, the sun shines, plants grow, wind blows and rivers flow.¹²

Make In India Opportunities In Renewable Energy Sector:

According to IMF World Economic Outlook-2021, India has become the third largest economy of the world after China and America on the basis of purchasing power parity and sixth in the world on the basis of nominal GDP and expected to continue its rapid-stride in urbanization and economic developments during next two to three decades.¹³ India is world's 3rd largest consumer of electricity and world's 3rd largest renewable energy producer with 38% (136 GW out of 373 GW) of total installed energy capacity in 2020 from renewable sources. Ernst & Young's (EY) 2021 Renewable Energy Country Attractiveness Index (RECAI) ranked India 3rd behind USA and China. In 2016 Paris Agreement's Intended Nationally Determined Contributions targets, India made commitment of producing 40% of its total electricity from non-fossil fuel sources by 2030. In 2018, India's Central Electricity Authority set a target of producing 57% of the total electricity from non-fossil fuels sources by 2027. India has also set a target of producing 175 GW by 2022 and 450 GW by 2030 from RE. As of September 2020, 89.22 GW solar energy is already operational, projects of 48.21 GW are at various stages of bidding.

In 2020, 3 of the world's top 5 largest solar parks were in India including world's largest 2255 MW Bhadla Solar Park in Rajasthan and world's second-largest Solar Park of 2000 MW Pavgada Solar Park Tumkur in Karnataka and 100 MW Kurnool in Andhra Pradesh. Similarly, Wind Power in India has a strong manufacturing base with 20 manufacturers of 53 different wind turbine models of international quality up to 3 MW in size with exports to Europe, the United States and other countries. Solar, Wind and run-of-the-river hydroelectricity are environment friendly cheaper power sources they are sued as "must-run" sources in India to cater for the base load, and the polluting and foreign-import dependent coal-fired power is increasingly being moved from the "must-run base load" power generation to the load following power

generation (mid-priced and mid-merit on-demand need-based intermittently-produced electricity) to meet the peaking demand only.

On the other hand, India initiative the International Solar Alliance (ISA) is now an alliance of 121 countries. India was world's first country to set up a ministry of non-conventional energy resources (Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) in early 1980s). Solar Energy Corporation of India (SECI), a public sector undertaking, is responsible for the development of solar energy

industry in India. Hydroelectricity is administered separately by the Ministry of power and not included in MNRE.¹⁴

India ranks the second position in terms of population that accounts to 17% of the world's overall population (more than 138 cr. in 2021). India is globally ranked 3rd in consumption of energy. In terms of installed capacity and investment in RE, the EY's RE Country Attractiveness Index (RECAI) ranking in July 2021. USA, China, and India scores like 70.71, 68.73 and 66.22 respectively.

Table-1

Technology	India	USA	China
Solar PV	62.7 (1)	57.6	60.3
Solar CSP Power Plants	09.2 (4)	46.2	54.3
Hydroelectricity	46.4 (3)	57.6	60.3
Biofuels	47.4 (10)	45.3	52.8
Onshore Wind Power	54.2 (6)	58.1	55.7
Offshore Wind Power	28.6 (29)	55.6	60.6
Geothermal Power	23.2 (16)	46.0	31.7

Sources : Renewable Energy Country Attractiveness Index (RECAI), July-2021.

Opportunities And Investments For Prosperous India By 2030:

The "Make in India" programme is one such effort in the direction of giving boost to the growth stride of the economy. The program strive to become "A major new national program, designed to facilitate investment, foster innovation, enhance skill development, protect intellectual property, and build best-in-class manufacturing infrastructure." (Make in India, 2015). The commerce and industry ministry has identified 25 sectors where incentives and support will be provided in an effort to further Prime Minister Narendra Modi's Make in India campaign. Thermal power and renewable energy are included in the selected sectors to boost the electricity production. As electricity acts as a prime-mover of the economy, it requires slightly higher growth rate than that of the economy to keep pace for a longer period.¹⁵ However, the following huge opportunities and investments for the biggest democratic country through make in India programmes by 2030 are given below.

- (i) The National Solar Mission was launched in 2010. The objective of the mission is to establish India as a global leader in solar energy. The target of the National Solar Mission has been up-seated to 100 GW from 20 GW of grid-connected solar power by 2022.¹⁶
- (ii) India has a wind potential of more than 300 GW (at hub height 100 meters), the solar potential of -750 GW, assuming 3% wasteland is made available Small Hydro potential of - 20 GW, and Bio-energy potential of 25 GW %.
- (iii) As per the Paris Accord on Climate Change, the Government of India has set a

target of adding 175 GW of renewable power by 2022, which includes 100 GW from solar, 60 GW from wind, 10 GW from biomass and 5 GW from small hydropower. This will offer massive investment opportunities across the value chain. This has further extended to 450 GW by 2030.

- (iv) India aims to achieve 40% of installed power generation capacity from non-fossil fuel sources and reduce emission intensity of GDP by 33-35 % from 2005 level by 2030. With the accomplishment of these ambitious targets, India will become one of the largest Green Energy producer in the world, surpassing several developed countries.
- (v) India submitted its Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to the UNFCCC, on its goal of installing 175 gigawatts (GW) of renewable power capacity by 2022 by setting a new target to increase the country's share of non-fossil-based installed electric capacity to 40 per cent by 2030.
- (vi) MNRE issues an issuance of a Concessional Custom Duty Certificate (CCDCs) for setting up projects for the generation of Compressed biogas using Urban and Industrial Waste of Renewable Nature.
- (vii) Emission reduction of 28% over 2005 levels, against the target of 35% by 2030 already achieved by India.
- (viii) India will produce more than three times nuclear power and it is expected to reach 22,480 MW by the year 2031, from the

- current 6780 MW as more nuclear power plants are also planned in future.
- (ix) An investment of INR 1810.56 cr. for 210 MW Luhri Stage-I Hydro Electric ' Project located on river Satluj was approved by Hon'ble PM Shri Narendra Modi. Through this project 758.20 mn units of electricity will generate annually. This will result in direct & indirect employment to around 2000 persons, which will boost socio-economic development of the State.
- (x) India has attracted \$ 64 bn Foreign investment and made India 4th largest and fastest-growing economy in the world. By 2022 share of RE will expand to 220 GW.¹⁷
- (xi) Pradhan Mantri Kisan Urja Suraksha Evam Uttan Mahabhiyan (PM-KUSUM) Scheme achieved enhanced solar capacity of 30.8 GW- 2022 with the reused central financial support of INR 34,035 cr.¹⁸
- (xii) The 'Grid Connected Solar Roof Top Programme' aims to achieve a cumulative capacity of 40 GW from Rooftop Solar (RTS) Projects by the year 2022. The programme will be implemented with/the total central financial support of INR 11,814 cr. through DISCOMs.¹⁹
- (xiii) In order to attract the large investment for the development of the Offshore wind energy sector in India, the Government of India under the 'National Offshore Wind Energy Policy' has announced to develop 5 GW of offshore wind energy project by 2022 and 30 GW by 2030.²⁰

India's renewable energy deployment plans for the coming decade are likely to generate business opportunities worth \$20 billion a year, Prime Minister Narendra Modi said on November 26, 2020. Inviting global investors to join what he termed India's unparalleled journey towards expanding power generation capacity so that each citizen got access to electricity, he said the country's renewable energy capacity was now the fourth largest in the world. In the last six years, we increased our installed RE capacity by two and a half times. . . it is growing at the fastest speed among all major countries. Even when it was not affordable, we invested in renewable energy , (and) now our investment and scale is bringing costs down," Mr Modi said at the inaugural session of the Global Renewable Energy Investment Meeting and Expo. "We are showing to the world that sound environmental policies can also be sound economics," he said, urging global investors to consider tapping the recently approved production-linked incentive scheme for manufacturing high efficiency solar power modules in the country. "There are huge renewable energy deployment plans

for the next decade. These are likely to generate business prospects of the order of around 20 billion dollars per year. I invite investors, developers and businesses to join India's renewable energy journey", he concluded.²¹ Today's slogan is 'Green Energy'. That's why, Green energy generation will create a demand for skill sets in the construction and installation of wind or solar farms which in turn have to be run and maintained and which will need its own skilled manpower. Transmission and distribution will follow and demand its own set of specialists focusing on transmission system and delivery within and between states while distribution service providers will secure service delivery and provision. Green energy is now an article of faith within and between nations while it is as clear to see that energy security is paramount for every country. The meeting point of these two aspirational roads, is the Energy Engineer. Someone who meets the criterion of saving the planet, while securing the nation.²²

Conclusion:

No doubt, the COVID-19 has completely changed our world particularly both in socially and economically. As a result the Corona Virus lockdown has immensely affected the biggest drop in energy demand in history, with only renewables managing to increase output through the crisis. As people around the world consume less oil, gas and coal, electricity generated from the wind and sun will keep flowing, resulting in an unprecedented 8% decline in global carbon dioxide emissions this year, according to a report from the International Energy Agency (IEA). Despite of the huge COVID-19 crisis, India will be the fastest growing economy in the world in 2021 and 2022 according IMP projection. The IMP has retained it's forecast of India's economic growth at 9.5 percent in 2021 and 8.5 percent in 2022. To retain the growth rate and to fulfill the energy demands, India targets 70% of our energy coming from renewable sources by 2050. That is why, Indian companies in the renewable sector should rise to the occasion like our IT companies and use 'Make in India', a catalyst for a high growth and create huge opportunities for the youth in our country in order to save the planet and securing the nation from the massive pollutions.

References

1. Special Report on Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Changes Mitigation – 2012 : Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), p.7.
2. Ibid, p.7.
3. Ibid, p.7.
4. The Hindu, June-16, 2021, p.8.
5. Special Report on Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Changes Mitigation – 2012 : Intergovernmental Panel on Climate

- Change (IPCC), p.7.
6. Kegley. Jr. Charles. W. (2006), “*World Politics : Trend and Transformation*”, University of South Carolina, p. 371.
7. Ibid. p.7.
8. Wikipedia : Renewable Energy – 2021.
9. Ibid.
10. The Hindu, June-16, 2021, p.8.
11. The U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA), November-1, 2020.
12. Ibid.
13. Renewable Energy in India – 2021 : Wikipedia.
14. Make in India and Future of Renewable Energy : Conference Proceedings “10th Anniversary-India-Japan Bilateral Impact of Make in India Efforts – 2015., p.2.
15. Annual Rept-2019-20, Ministry of New & Renewable Energy.
16. PIBRelease, <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReelasePage.aspx?PRID= 1672580>.
17. Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, https://mnre.gov.in/img/docuements/uploads/file_f-1607587283931.pdf.
18. Annual Report 2019-20, Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, https://mnre.gov.in/img/documents/uploads/file_f1597797108502.pdf.
19. Schemes, Ministry of New & Renewable Energy, <https://mnre.gov.in/soalr/schemes/>
20. Annual Report 2019-20, Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, https://mnre.gov.in/img/documents/uploads/file_f1597797108502.pdf.
21. The Hindu, November 26, 2020.
22. The Hindu, June 16, 2021.